

READING STRATEGIES AND READING COMPREHENSION OF THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the reading strategies and the reading comprehension of the senior high school Humanities and Social Sciences grade 11 students at Manuel S. Enverga Memorial School of Arts and Trades A.Y. 2020 – 2021. Specifically, it sought to answer the questions regarding the mean pre-test score of the students in the experimental group in their reading comprehension before using the reading strategies in terms of logical reasoning, text comprehension and vocabulary; the mean pre-test score of the students in the control group in their reading comprehension before using the modular instruction in terms of logical reasoning, text comprehension, and vocabulary; is the mean post test score of the students in the experimental group in reading comprehension after using the reading strategies in term of logical reasoning, text comprehension, and vocabulary; and the mean post-test score of the students in the control group in reading comprehension after using the modular instruction in terms of logical reasoning, text comprehension, and vocabulary. The significant difference between the pretest and post test scores of the students in reading comprehension before and after using reading strategies, the significant difference between the pre and post test scores of the students in reading comprehension before and after using modular instruction, and the significant difference between the post test scores of the students in reading comprehension after using reading strategies and modular instruction were also determined in this study which were computed using paired and independent t – test. The research design employed was quasi-experimental pretest-posttest non-equivalent group research design. The data gathering was made through a paper and pen pretest-posttest questionnaire which was validated by the researcher to two (2) mater teachers and one (1) principal and conducted to the sixty (60) Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences students of Manuel S. Enverga Memorial School of Arts and Trades A.Y. 2020 – 2021. Weighted mean and standard deviation of the pretest and posttest score of students were obtained to identify if the level of the student’s comprehension abilities fall under the identical level and t-test was used to obtain the significant difference between using the reading strategies and modular instruction in the comprehension abilities of the students. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. After the implementation of the reading strategies, the hypotheses which states that there is no significant difference between the pretest and post test scores of the students in reading comprehension before and after using reading strategies and there is no significant difference between the post test scores of the students in reading comprehension after using reading strategies and modular instruction are rejected. Findings revealed that: the respondents in the experimental group increase their reading comprehension after the implementation of the reading strategies when their posttest weighted mean score of 30.7333 is higher than their pre-test with a weighted mean score of 26.7667 with a mean difference of 3.967; the respondents in the controlled group resulted lower in the posttest with a weighted mean score of 19.667 that their pre-test with a weighted mean score of 21.8333 with a mean difference of 2.167; the

results between the pretest and posttest scores of both controlled and experimental groups showed that they score higher in the text comprehension than in logical reasoning and vocabulary; the mean difference of the posttest scores of the respondents in the experimental group with a weighted mean of 30.7333 and controlled group with a weighted mean of 19.667 is 11.067 with a standard deviation of 8.586 is significant. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were suggested: a) the teacher may take the initiative to observe not only the academic performance of the students based on the lessons but also their reading comprehension skills, in line with this, the teacher may identify the comprehension level of the students and utilize reading strategies if needed; the reading strategies may vary and may be suited to the student's needs; b) the students may help themselves on how to enhance their reading comprehension skill due to the fact that it is one of the vital requirements in everyday living, not just in academics but also in real life application most especially nowadays, where alternative learning delivery modalities were applied to the system of education such as online learning, modular distance learning, blended learning, radio-based instruction, and TV-based instruction; c) the administration may provide educational materials to be utilized to enhance the reading comprehension of the students for all grade levels especially in senior high school students who need to be well-equipped before entering the tertiary level in education.

Keywords: reading strategies, reading comprehension, logical reasoning, text comprehension